

Deposition methods govern the electrochemical performance of graphene-derivative functionalized screen-printed electrodes: A practical framework for electrode surface characterization

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Surface characterization
Inkjet printing
Drop-casting
Screen-printed electrode
Electrochemical sensor

ABSTRACT

The performance of functionalized electrochemical sensors is commonly linked to the intrinsic properties of the material used for electrode surface modification. However, the role of the deposition method itself is often overlooked, even though it critically defines the interfacial structure and batch-to-batch reproducibility. In addition, electrode functionalization is rarely accompanied by comprehensive surface characterization, which limits mechanistic interpretation and transferability of results. Here, we introduce a structured, multiscale characterization framework that isolates how deposition methods define the electrochemical interface on printed electrodes. A commercial screen-printed carbon electrode platform was functionalized with nitrogen-doped graphene acid using conventional drop-casting and inkjet printing as a controlled deposition strategy. Complementary local and electrode-scale analyses were used to quantify film homogeneity, thickness distribution, microtopography, wetting behavior, and coating integrity. These interfacial descriptors were systematically correlated with electrochemical performance using impedance spectroscopy and voltammetric benchmarking. Inkjet printing produced thin, laterally uniform coatings with enhanced wetting and significantly reduced electrode-to-electrode variability. In contrast, drop-casting resulted in edge-enriched films dominated by coffee-ring drying and pronounced interfacial heterogeneity. The electrochemical response was governed by the spatial accessibility and distribution of the functional layer rather than by the nominal deposited mass. This positions deposition technique among primary design parameters in electrochemical sensor development. The framework presented here provides a practical characterization and reporting protocol that supports reproducible and mechanistically interpretable optimization of functionalized electrochemical interfaces.

Introduction

Printed electrochemical devices have progressed from academic prototypes to platforms increasingly considered for analytical measurements in healthcare diagnostics [1], environmental monitoring [2],

wearable sensors [3], and crop health and precision agriculture [4]. In electrochemical (bio)sensors, performance is commonly enhanced through electrode surface functionalization to improve sensitivity and selectivity. This development has been supported by screen printing (SP), inkjet printing (IJP) and related thin-film approaches that allow

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electrodes and interconnects to be patterned on biodegradable plastics [5], paper [6,7], textiles [8], and other substrates that are challenging to address with conventional microfabrication. As the field moves beyond proof-of-concept demonstrations, reproducibility across batches and measurement settings becomes a central requirement [9]. In this context, particular attention has been directed toward how functional layers are introduced onto printed electrodes.

Most reported printed sensors are not fully printed in a strict fabrication sense [10–13]. Electrode geometries and contact layers are commonly produced by SP or other high-throughput techniques, while the functional layer is then added in a post-fabrication step [14–17]. In sensing, this functionalization is most commonly achieved by depositing nanomaterials (or biocomponents in biosensing) onto the working electrode surface, and it frequently governs the resulting sensitivity and selectivity. This functional layer may contain nanocarbons [18,19], metal nanostructures [20,21], redox mediators [22], catalysts [23,24], polymer films [25], or biorecognition components [26,27]. Drop-casting (DC) remains widely used for this purpose because it requires minimal equipment and is compatible with many dispersions [28–31]. However, reliance on manual deposition can introduce structural inconsistency [32]. Drying dynamics, droplet spreading, and particle redistribution during solvent evaporation may lead to changes in the local composition and thickness across the working area, particularly for suspensions containing polydisperse flakes or aggregates [33,34]. Aligning post-fabrication functionalization with the level of control used in electrode patterning is therefore an important step toward more consistent printed electrochemical interfaces.

The deposition technique should therefore be regarded as a primary electrochemical variable rather than a minor fabrication detail. The method used to deposit a functional material on a printed electrode influences the lateral homogeneity of coverage, the local thickness distribution, the micro- and nanoscale surface architecture, and the quality of electrical contact between the deposited layer and the underlying conductor [35,36]. Nonuniform films can create regions with different effective resistances and capacitances, altering the measured impedance response and can mask the interfacial kinetics [37]. Local thickness variations may also affect mass transport by introducing diffusion barriers and can shift the balance between faradaic and capacitive currents, particularly in voltametric measurements that rely on small signal changes [38,39]. In addition, percolation and contact quality within a nanomaterial network influence whether the functional layer provides efficient electron transport or behaves as a partially resistive coating [40]. Recent studies have shown that IJP can enable efficient and reproducible deposition of functional nanomaterials on electrode surfaces, while reducing material consumption and fabrication costs [35, 41–43]. With appropriate printing and drying conditions, this approach can promote more uniform coverage and narrower thickness distributions [44–46]. In contrast, DC frequently yields heterogeneous films shaped by evaporation- and surface-tension-driven flows, including coffee-ring formation and cracking, which tend to increase variability and hinder reproducible measurements [47,48]. From an electrochemical perspective, surface architecture is often the key factor shaping performance rather than a secondary consideration, and must be treated, characterized, and reported accordingly.

Current characterization practices in the literature often do not reflect this reality, and as a result, differences in electrochemical response are frequently attributed primarily to material chemistry [49, 50]. Many studies rely on a few microscopy images [51–53] and a limited electrochemical dataset [54,55] to justify performance differences between modified electrodes. Such reporting can confirm the presence of a coating, but it rarely quantifies spatial heterogeneity across the entire working area. Average roughness values, when reported, may hide local non-uniformities that influence current distribution and reaction environments [56,57]. Likewise, a single cyclic voltammogram cannot distinguish whether improved response arises from increased electroactive area, improved kinetics, altered mass

transport, or uncontrolled variations in coating thickness [58]. As a consequence, batch-to-batch variability is often underestimated, even though it can be non-negligible for printed and post-functionalized electrodes. The field would benefit from clearer standards for interface characterization, particularly for printed (bio)sensors where electrode-to-electrode variability directly affects evaluation of the recognition strategy. A practical approach would combine spatially resolved and complementary surface characterization with electrochemical methods that probe kinetics and interfacial properties. When mapping and topography measurements are linked to impedance spectroscopy, voltammetry, and appropriate controls, the resulting picture becomes predictive and enables reproducible design decisions [59,60].

In this work, we present a controlled comparison that isolates the role of deposition technique in shaping the electrochemical interface on an electrode. We use a commercial screen-printed carbon electrode (SPCE) platform and functionalize it with nitrogen-doped graphene acid (NGA) [61] water-based suspension using two different routes: conventional DC and IJP, while the bare electrode serves as the baseline. The functional ink is identical in composition and concentration across the two functionalization routes, so that differences in performance can be attributed solely to deposition rather than to formulation. We then combine spatially resolved surface characterization (3D confocal topography, profilometry, atomic force microscopy, Raman mapping, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy; see Table 1 for the overview of characterization methods and their key parameters) with rigorous electrochemical evaluation to establish explicit links between surface architecture, interface quality, and electrochemical performance. By treating deposition as a controllable electrochemical variable and demonstrating how its consequences can be characterized, this study provides a methodological framework for evaluating printed electrode interfaces prior to their integration into application-driven (bio)sensing platforms. The broader aim is to support more reproducible, comparable, and mechanistically grounded research in printed electrochemistry by promoting interface characterization standards that match the maturity of modern printing technologies.

Materials and methods

Reagents and materials

Graphite, fluorinated polymer > 61 wt.% F – GF, (Millipore Sigma), sodium azide 99% – NaN_3 (Millipore Sigma), dimethylformamide pure – DMF (Lach:ner), absolute ethanol – EtOH (Penta), nitric acid 65% – HNO_3 (Lach:ner) and acetone 99% (Millipore Sigma) were used for synthesis of NGA. Potassium ferricyanide(III) – $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ (Millipore Sigma), Dopamine hydrochloride (Millipore Sigma), Phosphate-buffered saline – PBS (Millipore Sigma), Ultrapure water (18 M Ω cm) were used to prepare the electrolyte solution. All adhesion tapes were purchased from 3M company.

Synthesis of nitrogen-doped graphene acid (NGA)

The synthesis was performed as described in the previous report [61]. A total of 5 g of GF was dispersed in 150 ml of DMF in a glass flask and stirred for 72 h, and subsequently sonicated for 4 h. Then, 15 g of NaN_3 was added to the prepared solution, which was transferred to a round-bottom flask and stirred in an oil bath at 130 °C for 3 days under reflux. After the reaction, nitrogen-doped graphene [62] was washed with DMF (3 \times), acetone (3 \times), ethanol (3 \times), distilled water (3 \times) and hot distilled water (2 \times) using centrifugation (14,000 rcf). The cleaned nitrogen-doped graphene was treated with 45% HNO_3 for 48 h at 100 °C in an oil bath under reflux. The product was then purified by filtration (Whatman cellulose membrane filter, pore size 200 nm) with hot distilled water (4 \times), distilled water (4 \times), and further purified by dialysis (dialysis tubing cellulose membrane 14 kDa cutoff). Purified NGA was then filtered through a 450 nm membrane filter to obtain the

Table 1

Overview of methods used for the characterization of electrode surfaces and their key parameters.

Method	Lateral resolution (x-y)	Vertical resolution (z)	Measurable height range ^a	Sample preparation time (min)	Measurement time	Typical cost per measurement (EUR) ^b
SEM	1–5 nm	Not true height	μm–mm (apparent only)	5–60 (mounting, coating)	5–30 min	50–300
XPS	10–100 μm (down to ~1–5 μm with micro-XPS)	~1–10 nm (information depth)	~1–10 nm (surface sensitive)	10–30	90 min–hours	100–500+
Raman mapping	1 μm (spectra point) ^c	1–5 μm	10–50 μm	0–10	60 min–hours	100–500+
CLSM	200–300 nm	5–20 nm	10–100+ μm	0–10	5–30 min	20–100
Stylus profilometry	1–10 μm	0.1–1 nm	1 mm	0–5	5–20 min	5–30
AFM	1–10 nm (can be sub nm)	0.05–0.3 nm	up to 10 μm	10–60	60 min–hours	50–300
Adhesion tape test	NA	NA	NA	0–5	5–20 min	3
Contact angle	NA	NA	NA	0–10	5–20 min	5

^a Measurable height range refers to the approximate vertical dimension (surface feature height or depth) that can be reliably quantified by the technique under typical operating conditions.

^b Costs are order-of-magnitude estimates for shared academic/industrial facilities (instrument amortization + operator time).

^c Can be enhanced by standard TERS method (AFM/STM-based) to 10–20 nm lateral resolution.

NGA fraction with flake size < 450 nm. Lastly, the NGA concentration in dispersion was adjusted to 2 mg mL⁻¹.

Characterization methods

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were obtained by JEOL-7900F SEM microscope and Scios Dual Beam (ThermoFisher Scientific) with accelerating voltage of 5 kV. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images were obtained by JEOL-2100 TEM microscope with accelerating voltage of 200 kV. Samples were sputter-coated with gold (20 mA, 36 s) to reduce charging during SEM imaging. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) coupled with evolved gas analysis (EGA) was performed using a Netzsch STA 449 C Jupiter simultaneous thermal analyzer at a heating rate of 5 °C min⁻¹ under a nitrogen flow. The masses of the evolved gaseous species in the *m/z* range 16–46 were monitored using a QMS 403 Aeolos mass spectrometer (Netzsch), also under a nitrogen flow. To minimize the mass spectrometer's overload from physisorbed water, the sample chamber was preheated to 100 °C and then cooled to room temperature prior to analysis. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were performed using a Nexsa G2 spectrometer from Thermo Fisher Scientific, equipped with an Al K α radiation source. The obtained data were analyzed with Advantage software. Confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM) was conducted with a LEXT OLS5000 laser-scanning microscope (Olympus) with 4 K scanning technology. Profilometry surface measurements were performed using Dektak XT stylus profilometer (Bruker) with stylus width of 12.5 μm and stylus force of 3 mg. Atomic force microscopy (AFM) images were obtained by SPM NTEGRA (NT-MDT) in semi-contact mode with HA-NC tips. Raman mapping was performed using a confocal dispersive Raman microscope inVia Reflex DUV-NIR (Renishaw), with a 266 nm laser and a 40x objective at 100% laser power. The acquisition time was 30 s with 1 accumulation per spectrum. Contact angle measurements were made using a Krüss Dropshare Analyser in the sessile drop configuration. Distilled water droplets (5 μL) were dispensed using a Nordson needle (0.5 mm inner diameter). Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra were obtained with a Thermo Nicolet iS5 FTIR spectrometer, equipped with a Smart Orbit ATR accessory featuring a ZnSe crystal.

Electrochemical measurements

All electrochemical measurements were conducted using a Metrohm Autolab PGSTAT128N potentiostat (MetrohmAutolab B.V., Netherlands) controlled by the NOVA software package (version 2.1). The experimental setup employed a three-electrode configuration

utilizing commercially available Metrohm DropSens SPCE. All electrochemical measurements were carried out at room temperature (22 ± 2 °C) in 0.01 mol L⁻¹ PBS (pH 7.4).

Modification of SPCEs

Modification of SPCEs was performed by two methods. (a) drop-casting: 15 μL of NGA dispersion (2 mg mL⁻¹) was pipetted onto the working electrode (WE) of SPCE, and allowed to dry at room temperature, forming a characteristic film. (b) inkjet printing: NGA was deposited using a Fujifilm Dimatix Materials printer, model DMP-2850, equipped with Dimatix Drop Manager V3.2.4.2 software. Samba cartridges equipped with piezoelectric printheads (12 jets; nominal drop volume 2.4 pL) were used. All layers were printed at 2540 dpi (drop spacing 10 μm; printhead angle 1.7°). The cartridge temperature was kept at the default value (28 °C), and the print height was set to 1 mm. Prior to printing, the jetting waveform and driving voltage were optimized to generate spherical droplets without ligaments or satellite droplets. To maximize printing quality, a single jet was used for printing. After printing five layers, the SPCEs were stored in a desiccator until further use.

Adhesion and wash stability measurements

The adhesion experiment was adapted from a cross-hatch tape test, using adhesive tapes with well-defined peel forces. Each tape was cut to 1 cm × 6 cm. One-third of the tape length was pressed onto the SPCE working electrode, while the remaining two-thirds were left unattached to facilitate handling. After a few seconds, the tape was peeled from the SPCE surface at 45°. Finally, the tape was inspected for carbon/graphene residues, indicating partial delamination of the coating.

Wash stability was evaluated with electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). Briefly, 50 μL of electrolyte (5 mmol L⁻¹ K₃[Fe(CN)₆] in 0.01 mol L⁻¹ PBS, pH 7.4) was pipetted onto the SPCE electrode area, and cyclic voltammetry (CV) followed by EIS was performed. After each measurement, SPCE was thoroughly rinsed with distilled water and dried under nitrogen stream, and the same electrochemical protocol was repeated. This procedure was carried out for a total of five measurements (wash 0–4), corresponding to four intermediate washing steps.

Results and discussion

Surface microstructure

First, we examined surface of the WE. Top-view SEM is an efficient starting point because it directly reveals general interaction between the deposited material and the porous SPCE substrate. The bare SPCE surface consists of a heterogeneous carbon network with micrometer-scale features and open porosity (Fig. 1a). After IJP functionalization, the NGA forms a uniform coating that closely follows the native texture of the carbon surface (Fig. 1b), with deposited graphene flakes of about 300 nm in lateral size (Fig. S1). This morphology is consistent with a

layer-by-layer build-up resulting from sequential picolitre droplet deposition, which favors homogeneous coverage and the formation of continuous electronic pathways to the underlying carbon. Additional SEM images acquired from the central region of the bare SPCE and the IJP-functionalized SPCE further confirm that the IJP coating remains comparatively uniform across the full modified area (Fig. S2a,b). In contrast, DC produces an inhomogeneous film with a characteristic coffee-ring pattern (Fig. 1c). After drying, most of the material accumulates at the edge of the droplet contact line due to outward capillary or Marangoni [47] flow during solvent evaporation. Such evaporation-driven redistribution can also introduce local stress within the drying film, leading to cracking or discontinuities and increasing the

Fig. 1. Surface and cross-sectional SEM images of the WE in SPCEs before and after NGA modification. Top-view SEM images at increasing magnification for (a) bare SPCE, (b) SPCE IJP NGA, and (c) SPCE DC NGA. Schematic illustrations of the corresponding electrode modification (left) and SEM cross-section images (right) for (d) bare SPCE, (e) SPCE IJP NGA, and (f) SPCE DC NGA, with the deposited film thickness marked in red.

likelihood of poorly adhered regions that may detach during handling or upon electrolyte wetting. SEM images from the centre region of the drop-casted SPCE show that graphene is also present, but in substantially lower quantity than at the ring region, and on the IJP-functionalized SPCE, despite the higher total amount of deposited material (Fig. S2c). A cross-sectional SEM provides additional insight into the substrate architecture (Fig. 1d) and the thickness of the deposited NGA layers. The inkjet-printed coating forms a thin, continuous layer approximately 0.3 μm thick (Fig. 1e), suggesting good interfacial contact with the porous carbon matrix. In contrast, DC produces a markedly thicker deposit, reaching 6.4 μm at the raised rim, and the cross-sections reveal a less uniform, locally disrupted electrode-coating interface (Fig. 1f).

In electrochemical systems where the substrate and the deposited material are both carbon-based, as in this case, SEM provides limited contrast and cannot reliably distinguish between exposed SPCE and NGA-coated regions. SEM establishes the surface architecture, but it does not unambiguously identify which domains correspond to the native carbon ink versus the NGA overlayer. To resolve this, we next assess the near-surface chemical composition by XPS, which provides element-specific contrast between pristine SPCE and NGA-modified SPCEs. Three measurement spots were positioned along a radial line across the circular WE to obtain representative atomic composition (Fig. S3a). The bare SPCE surface is dominated by carbon (Fig. S3b), consistent with a network of linked carbon particles and platelet-like additive/binder components observed by SEM. The NGA-modified electrodes show increased O and N contents in the survey spectra (Fig. S3c,d), consistent with the oxygen- and nitrogen-enriched composition of NGA (Fig. S4a) and indicating surface coverage by the deposited layer. At the same time, a slight increase in C content and decrease in N content might indicate a locally reduced NGA fraction toward the electrode center and/or higher accumulation toward the periphery.

To identify which carbon functionalities are introduced at the electrolyte-facing interface (beyond the survey-level O and N enrichment), the high-resolution (HR) C 1s spectra were deconvoluted for each of the three measurement spots (Fig. 2a). The pristine SPCE spectra are dominated by the graphitic and aliphatic carbon contributions (C–C sp^2 and C–C sp^3), together with a C–N/O/Cl-related component and a weak π - π^* satellite (Fig. 2b). After NGA deposition, additional oxygen-containing components become clearly resolved at all inspected locations, namely carbonyl (C=O) and carboxyl (O–C=O) contributions, together with other oxygenated functionalities (Fig. 2c,d), consistent with HR XPS spectra (Fig. S4b–d), FTIR spectroscopy (Fig. S5) and STA-EGA analysis (Fig. S6a,b) of pristine NGA. Their consistent appearance across spots provides direct evidence that the NGA layer enriches the near-surface region in oxygen-containing functional groups, with carbonyl- and, critically, carboxyl-type species representing dominant contributions (see detailed composition in Panáček D. et al., [63]) which are the groups most directly implicated in interfacial charge effects and hydrogen-bonding interactions relevant for electroanalysis. This interpretation is further supported by STA-EGA, which shows that the thermal decomposition of NGA is dominated by CO_2 evolution, indicating that carboxyl-type groups represent the major thermally labile oxygen-containing functionality in the material. Quantification of these oxygenated components further indicates that IJP yields a slightly more uniform lateral presentation of carboxyl-related carbon species across the WE. Specifically, the O–C=O peak area remains tightly clustered for IJP-functionalized SPCEs (15.1–16.0%), whereas drop-casted SPCEs show a broader spot-to-spot spread (13.4–15.6%) (Tab. S1). HR XPS confirms that both deposition routes deliver the chemically relevant oxygenated NGA signature at the surface, but it also suggests that IJP provides a more even distribution of carboxylated groups across the electrode footprint.

Raman spectroscopy further provides a direct contrast between pristine SPCE carbon and NGA flakes through their different defect

populations. NGA structure is rich in defects (Fig. S7), with a higher fraction of sp^3 -type carbon environments which give rise to defect-related vibrations reflected in the D band. The graphitic sp^2 network contributes to the G band, which is also present in NGA, but dominates in pristine SPCE (Fig. 3a). With this in mind, spatial Raman mapping was applied to each sample over a representative area of $2100 \mu\text{m} \times 100 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 3b). To compare samples, the ratio of D and G band areas ($A_{\text{D}}/A_{\text{G}}$) served as an indicator, since $A_{\text{D}}/A_{\text{G}}$ increases markedly when NGA is present (Fig. 3c). It should be noted, however, that in NGA-containing regions the apparent broadening of the D band region may be influenced by a local fluorescence background, which also contributes to the fitted D band area and, to a lesser extent, to the G band area. Therefore, the fitted D band region should be understood as reflecting both defect-related Raman scattering and the background contribution associated with the presence of NGA. On the other hand, because this fluorescence is observed only in NGA-containing regions, it further enhances the contrast in Raman mapping. The resulting Raman maps (Fig. 3d) translate this spectral contrast into a spatial measure of NGA coverage and availability. For drop-casted SPCEs, the $A_{\text{D}}/A_{\text{G}}$ ratio remains evenly high across the footprint of the original droplet contact, but outside of the coffee-ring region the signal collapses to low $A_{\text{D}}/A_{\text{G}}$ values, indicating that the NGA structure is largely absent there. IJP-functionalized SPCEs show a more uniform $A_{\text{D}}/A_{\text{G}}$ distribution across the mapped path. One should keep in mind, however, that SEM, XPS and Raman mapping probe the near-surface region (on the order of nanometers [64,65]), and therefore cannot capture the lateral and vertical thickness distribution of the deposited layer. That is why more in-depth characterization, including mapping and topography techniques, needs to follow.

Coating topography

While electron microscopy reveals how NGA is deposited on local features of the porous carbon, reproducible electrochemistry depends equally on how uniformly the modification spans the whole WE. We used electrode-scale mapping to compare thickness uniformity across the active area for IJP and DC. CLSM maps (Fig. 4a–c) directly capture drying-induced redistribution as a height profile across the full electrode area. The IJP coating largely preserves the baseline profile of the SPCE, consistent with a thin and relatively uniform layer. In contrast, DC introduces a pronounced raised rim, consistent with evaporation-driven redistribution, implying a center–edge gradient in layer thickness that can modulate local accessibility and mass transport. The same measurement provides reflectance intensity maps (Fig. 4d–f). Intensity contrast arises from differences in optical response and microtexture between the porous carbon matrix and NGA-coated regions. The SPCEs functionalized by IJP show a more homogeneous signal across the selected area, indicating continuous coverage achieved by high-precision inkjet printer, whereas drop-casted SPCEs show a stronger contrast between central and peripheral regions, consistent with redistribution during drying. The magnified regions (Fig. 4g–i) support the interpretation. Confocal mapping thus turns the earlier qualitative observation of coffee-ring formation into a measurable spatial constraint.

Confocal measurements reveal macroscopic height variations, but electrochemical behavior is also governed by microtopography that defines the effective wetted interface. Stylus profilometry was used to quantify height profiles along defined line scans (Fig. 5a), capturing how each modification alters the WE contour. The native concave profile of the bare SPCE is shown in Fig. 5b. After IJP functionalization, the height profile largely follows the baseline shape of the pristine SPCE, indicating that the deposited NGA layer conforms to the existing electrode topography. In contrast, DC introduces an additional height contribution at the perimeter, consistent with the accumulation caused by the coffee-ring effect. AFM provides complementary microscale topography over much smaller scan areas than profilometry and enables quantification of micro-/nanoscale roughness (Fig. 5c,d). Both NGA modifications show

Fig. 2. HR XPS spectra of C 1s analysis of bare and NGA-modified SPCEs. (a) Photographs of SPCE indicating the XPS measurement spots. Deconvoluted C 1s spectra collected at three positions across the WE (spots 1–3) for (b) bare SPCE, (c) SPCE IJP NGA, and (d) SPCE DC NGA.

Fig. 3. Raman characterization of the WE in bare and NGA-modified SPCEs. (a) Representative Raman spectrum and deconvolution of the carbon D and G bands for SPCE bare. (b) Photograph of the SPCE showing the Raman mapping track (2100 μm × 100 μm). (c) Representative Raman spectrum and deconvolution of the carbon D and G bands for SPCE in the presence of NGA. (d) Spatial mapping of the D/G peak area ratio (A_D/A_G) across a line scan region on the WE of each SPCE type.

higher roughness compared to the bare SPCE, as reflected by increased root mean square roughness (R_q) and arithmetic mean roughness (R_a) (Tab. S2). Notably, the IJP samples exhibit the highest absolute roughness, but also the lowest R_q/R_a ratio. This suggests a more evenly distributed microtexture rather than occasional extreme features. In contrast, the higher R_q/R_a ratios for the bare and DC-modified electrodes indicate a more skewed height distribution, in which the overall roughness is more strongly influenced by infrequent extreme features. This particular characterization sequence, profilometry followed by AFM, is critical because it separates two effects that are often blended: more material does not necessarily translate into a larger electrochemically accessible area if material is redistributed into thick rims or forms locally disconnected domains.

Interface quality

The previous sections show that IJP and DC produce markedly different coating architectures, from thin uniform layers to edge-thickened rims. To translate these morphological differences into an electrochemical interpretation, we next assess practical factors that directly affect electrode performance, particularly the stability of the deposited layer during handling and repeated exposure to electrolyte, as even a chemically active surface is of limited relevance if it lacks mechanical robustness under routine measurement conditions. Adhesive tapes with well-defined peel forces were used to assess dry adhesion. The carbon substrate began to detach at peel forces of 2.6 N cm⁻¹ and above, whereas NGA-modified SPCE showed no delamination in NGA-covered areas. This suggests that NGA modification does not weaken the SPCE

surface and may even reinforce the near-surface cohesion of the printed carbon matrix (Fig. 6a). However, dry adhesion is insufficient for electrochemical reliability, as printed sensors operate under electrolyte wetting. Wash stability was therefore evaluated by repeating EIS measurements with rinsing and drying between cycles, tracking the interfacial contribution through the real part of the complex capacitance, calculated from impedance spectra using the following equation [66]:

$$C' = \frac{Z''}{2\pi f(Z'^2 + Z''^2)}$$

where C' stands for the real part of the complex capacitance, f is the frequency, Z' is the real impedance, and Z'' is the imaginary part of impedance. Consecutive wash steps caused a progressive reduction in capacitance for NGA-modified SPCEs (Fig. 6b), consistent with partial removal of the deposited layer during repeated electrolyte exposure. Correspondingly, the associated Bode phase evolution shifted toward the response of the underlying SPCE, supporting the view that the deposited layer contributes an additional interfacial element that can diminish with repeated wet handling (Fig. 6c,d).

The stability tests above indicated that NGA coverage can be non-uniform and can evolve upon wet handling. We probe the same interface from a complementary angle, i.e. how readily the electrolyte can wet and access the WE. On porous SPCEs, the apparent contact angle is not only a surface property. It reflects the balance between droplet spreading and penetration into the porous matrix, and it is therefore sensitive to whether hydrophilic NGA or the more hydrophobic native carbon dominates the exposed surface. Bare SPCEs remain relatively

Fig. 4. Confocal topography and reflectance mapping of the WE in bare and NGA-modified SPCEs. (a–c) Confocal height maps of the WE area for SPCE bare, SPCE IJP NGA, and SPCE DC NGA. (d–f) Corresponding confocal intensity maps acquired over the same areas. (g–i) Magnified views of central regions.

Fig. 5. Macro- and microtopography of the WE in bare and NGA-modified SPCEs. (a) Photograph of the SPCE indicating the profilometry line scan positions (1–5). (b) Representative profilometry height profiles for each type of SPCE (left), and the box plot summarizing the distribution of surface height (right). (c) AFM 3D topography images acquired on the WE surface for each SPCE type. (d) AFM height profiles illustrating local height differences.

Fig. 6. Adhesion and wash stability of NGA films on the WE of SPCEs. (a) Qualitative tape adhesion test of bare and NGA-modified SPCEs using adhesive tapes with defined peel forces (values above images). (b) Change in capacitance of each SPCE type during consecutive wash steps (wash 0–4). (c) Bode phase plots during the wash sequence for SPCE IJP NGA. (d) Bode phase plots during the wash sequence for SPCE DC NGA, illustrating the shift of the characteristic interfacial response.

hydrophobic due to their low oxygen content, resulting in higher contact angles. In contrast, NGA introduces oxygen- and nitrogen-containing groups that increase hydrophilicity and promote wetting. Representative images of contact angle measurements are shown in Fig. 7a. The experiment was performed in a sessile-drop configuration where a droplet placed on the WE was recorded with a camera in a horizontal setup (Fig. 7b). Wettability improved the most for IJP, where the more uniform coating produces a substantially lower contact angle compared with DC. DC modification improves wettability to a lesser extent, which is consistent with partial coverage and a larger contribution from regions dominated by the original SPCE surface. The extracted contact angle values, together with their statistical evaluation across four individual electrodes for each variant, are provided in Fig. 7c.

Electrochemical benchmark

With film morphology, composition, electrode-scale uniformity, mechanical robustness, and wettability established, we next designed electrochemical benchmarking procedure to determine how the interface structure translates into electrochemical response. For these purposes a standard outer-sphere redox probe [56] 5 mmol L⁻¹ K₃[Fe(CN)₆] was used. Phosphate buffered saline (PBS) of final concentration 0.01 mol L⁻¹ was added to ensure sufficient ionic conductivity.

EIS can provide an interface-resolved readout through equivalent circuit fitting, where it separates charge transfer resistance (R_{CT}) and capacitive contributions that are strongly affected by coating continuity, wetting, and electrical contact to the porous carbon matrix. EIS measurements were performed in the presence of the redox probe (5 mmol L⁻¹ K₃[Fe(CN)₆] in 0.01 mol L⁻¹ PBS pH 7.4) under following

Fig. 7. Wettability of bare and NGA-modified SPCEs. (a) Representative side-view images of water droplets on the WE during a measurement of each sample, with marked contact angles. (b) Schematic of the contact angle measurement setup on the SPCE platform. (c) Statistical analysis of measured contact angle values from quadruplicate for each variant; boxes show interquartile range, whiskers, median, and mean.

parameters: applied potential 100 mV, 50 frequencies ranging from 10,000 Hz to 0.1 Hz in logarithmic steps. Nyquist plots (Fig. 8a) show a single dominant semicircle for the bare SPCE, while NGA-modified SPCEs display two partially overlapping arcs, indicating an additional interfacial process/contribution introduced by the NGA layer. From equivalent circuit fitting (Fig. S8a,b), the solution resistance (R_s) corresponds to the resistance of the electrolyte solution. Two charge

transfer resistances (R_{CT1} and R_{CT2}), are assigned to the bare substrate and NGA interface. The capacitive response of the electrode interface is modelled by an ideal capacitor (C_{DL}) when behavior is near-ideal and by a constant phase element (CPE) when non-ideal (surface roughness, porosity, or inhomogeneous current distribution) behavior is evident [67,68]. The reported total charge transfer resistance, R_{CT} , was calculated as the sum of two fitted components, R_{CT1} and R_{CT2} . (Fig. 8b). R_{CT}

Fig. 8. Impedance response of bare and NGA-modified SPCEs. (a) Representative Nyquist plots recorded in the presence of the redox probe (5 mmol L⁻¹ K₃[Fe(CN)₆] in 0.01 mol L⁻¹ PBS pH 7.4), inset: equivalent electrochemical circuit used to model the impedance response of NGA-modified SPCEs. (b) Statistical analysis of R_{CT} values extracted from the Nyquist plots fitting (in triplicates) for each electrode type, bars represent mean \pm confidence interval and the mean is marked by a horizontal line.

reflects how easily electrons are exchanged between the redox couple and the electrode surface. Both NGA modifications reduced R_{CT} compared to the bare SPCE 1088Ω , with inkjet-printed NGA showing the lowest R_{CT} 533Ω and, importantly, the smallest spread between electrodes. This trend follows directly from the structural evidence: IJP produces a thin, laterally uniform film with good wetting and stable adhesion, which promotes a reproducible electronically connected and electrolyte-accessible interface. In contrast, DC creates a thicker film with coffee-ring-induced accumulation and local discontinuities, so the effective active area and interfacial contact vary more strongly from electrode to electrode, increasing variability because different parts of the nominal working area do not contribute equally.

Translating R_{CT} into a kinetic metric reinforces the same conclusion. The heterogeneous electron transfer rate constant (k^0) was calculated using equation [69]:

$$R_{CT} = \frac{RT}{n^2 F^2 A C k^0}$$

where F stands for Faraday constant, A for electrode area, C for redox probe concentration. The resulting k^0 values were calculated to be $3.90 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ for bare SPCE, $7.96 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ for IJP-modified SPCE and $4.68 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ for DC-modified SPCE. Thus, NGA offers the potential for improved interfacial kinetics, but the extent of improvement depends on whether the deposited material forms a continuous and well-adhered layer rather than a locally thick and discontinuous one.

To connect kinetics with interface accessibility, the electrochemically active surface area (ECSA) was estimated from peak current measured by cyclic voltammetry at scan rate of 0.01 V s^{-1} . The measured peak current was used in the Randles-Ševčík equation [70]:

$$A = \frac{I_p}{2.69 \times 10^5 n^{3/2} D^{1/2} C \nu^{1/2}}$$

where A stands for ECSA, I_p for peak current, D for diffusion coefficient ($7.17 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [71]), C for redox probe concentration, ν for scan rate. The resulting ECSA was calculated to be 0.063 cm^2 for bare SPCE, 0.072 cm^2 for IJP-modified SPCE and 0.058 cm^2 for DC-modified SPCE, which is consistent with IJP providing more effective utilization of the modified surface under electrolyte wetting, rather than simply increasing deposited mass.

CV scan-rate(ν)-dependent studies provide a complementary view to EIS by separating kinetic indicators from accessibility effects. They reveal whether the response is controlled mainly by diffusion to an accessible surface, or whether the coating introduces additional barriers

through thickness gradients, partial blocking, or incomplete electrical coupling. The linear dependence of both anodic and cathodic peak currents on $\nu^{1/2}$ indicates that the redox process remains predominantly diffusion-controlled in all cases, i.e., there is no transition to a purely adsorption-controlled regime, but the slopes differ (Fig. 9a). The central outcome is the decoupling of two metrics in the DC samples – drop-casted electrodes can show lower peak current densities than bare SPCE, even though their peak-to-peak separation ΔE_p is smaller (Fig. 9b). This combination is informative because peak current density and ΔE_p probe different aspects of the interface. Peak current density is strongly influenced by the electrochemically accessible fraction of the WE, i.e., the fraction of the surface that is simultaneously wetted, electronically connected, and reachable by the redox probe. In the DC case, the thicker, partially blocking coating and locally disrupted interface can reduce the effective participation of the nominal working area, either by partially blocking pore access or by creating regions where NGA is present but not efficiently coupled to the underlying carbon. By contrast, ΔE_p reflects the kinetics of the redox exchange at the active interface, and it can decrease when NGA provides more favorable interfacial energetics and/or higher local electronic conductivity at contacted regions. Thus, DC may enhance local charge-transfer kinetics at the regions that remain active, while reducing the fraction of the WE that is effectively electrochemically accessible. IJP largely avoids this trade-off, providing improved kinetics while preserving accessibility, consistent with the thin, laterally uniform film, the more homogeneous NGA availability, and the improved wetting established earlier.

This distinction becomes clearer as the electrochemical measurements move from an outer-sphere redox probe to an analyte that directly interacts with the functional groups of NGA. Dopamine was used as a representative target because its oxidation on NGA is not solely governed by electron-transfer kinetics but also by adsorption and interfacial interactions with the functional layer. Previous work [42] attributes the enhanced dopamine oxidation on NGA to its affinity for carboxyl groups, reinforced by the local chemical environment created by nitrogen functionalities. As a result, the dopamine signal should scale primarily with the electrochemically accessible fraction of NGA, i.e., the area that is simultaneously exposed to the electrolyte and electronically coupled to the SPCE, rather than with the nominal deposited mass. This behavior is captured by the dopamine response (Fig. 10). The schematic in Fig. 10a summarizes the interaction-driven view, where dopamine approaches and reacts at the NGA-modified interface. Inkjet-printed NGA produces the highest oxidation signal (Fig. 10b), in direct agreement with the earlier structural evidence of electrode-scale coverage and accessibility. Raman and optical mapping showed NGA distributed across the working area, and contact-angle measurements confirmed

Fig. 9. Study of the dependence of current density on scan rate in case of bare and NGA-modified SPCEs. (a) Anodic and cathodic peak current densities obtained from cyclic voltammograms at exponentially increasing scan rates. (b) Peak-to-peak separation as a function of scan rate, for each SPCE type.

Fig. 10. Dopamine sensing on bare and NGA-modified SPCEs. (a) Schematic illustration of dopamine adsorption on NGA deposited on the SPCE. (b) Baseline corrected differential pulse voltammograms of 1 mmol L⁻¹ dopamine (0.01 mol L⁻¹ PBS pH 7.4), shown as mean curves with standard deviation bands based on triplicate measurements, for each SPCE type.

efficient wetting, together with electrochemical measurements showing that IJP maximizes the fraction of NGA that can participate in adsorption-driven dopamine oxidation. Drop-casted NGA, despite depositing a thicker and more edge-enriched film, still increases the dopamine oxidation response relative to bare SPCE, indicating that NGA surface chemistry remains active where it is accessible. However, the gain is smaller than for IJP-modified variant, consistent with the confocal and profilometry results showing redistribution into a coffee-ring rim, which ultimately results in limited NGA availability outside that region. These results show that dopamine electrochemical response is not a direct function of applied material or deposited mass. Instead, it is controlled by interface utilization, i.e., the density of accessible functional sites within a continuous, wetted, and electronically connected coating, which is set by the deposition method.

Conclusion

In this work, we systematically compared IJP and DC as two deposition routes for constructing NGA-modified SPCE interfaces, using the same NGA formulation to isolate the effect of deposition method. By combining complementary surface, thickness, topography, stability, and wetting characterization techniques with electrochemical benchmarking, we identified which interface parameters control performance and reproducibility. Although the experiments were conducted using a specific NGA derivative, the observed relationships between deposition method, film morphology, and electrochemical behavior are likely relevant to other graphene-based electrode modifiers such as graphene oxide, reduced graphene oxide, or heteroatom-doped graphene materials, where flake distribution, aggregation, and surface wetting similarly determine the accessibility of electroactive sites. Collectively, the structural characterization showed that IJP produced a thin, laterally uniform NGA coating with stable interfacial contact and improved wetting, whereas DC yielded an edge-enriched, thicker deposit shaped by coffee-ring drying and greater spatial heterogeneity. Electrochemical benchmarking with an outer-sphere redox probe linked these differences to lower and more reproducible R_{CT} , higher k^0 , and more effective utilization of the electrode surface modified by IJP. Moving to dopamine, an analyte that interacts with NGA functional groups, provided an application-relevant confirmation that signal enhancement follows accessible NGA coverage rather than nominal loading: the highest response was obtained when NGA was distributed across the working area and efficiently wetted. Taken together, these complementary results show that electrochemical performance cannot be inferred from material identity or nominal loading alone. Instead, it is governed by

how effectively the deposition route translates the active material into a continuous, wetted, and electronically coupled interface that exposes functional sites to the electrolyte. For researchers working with other graphene derivatives or nanostructured electrode modifiers, these results emphasize that controlling particles distribution and achieving uniform coverage across the working electrode area can be as important as the intrinsic properties of the nanomaterial itself. Practically, this work provides a methodological framework for evaluating modified electrode interfaces prior to application-driven sensing studies, demonstrating the value of combining morphological imaging, topographical analysis, and electrochemical probing to obtain a more complete understanding of modified electrode interfaces, and it highlights deposition choice as a central parameter for achieving reproducible and interpretable electrochemical performance. Such an approach may serve as a useful guideline for researchers aiming to rationally design and characterize modified electrode surfaces across a variety of materials and sensing applications.

Declaration of generative AI in scientific writing

While preparing this work, the authors used ChatGPT to improve the readability and language of the manuscript. After using this tool, the authors carefully reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the publication's content. All images in this work were created using licensed graphic software, without the use of artificial intelligence.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Matěj Jendrišák: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Martin-Alex Nalepa:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Vítězslav Hrubý:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Investigation. **Petr Jakubec:** Writing – review & editing. **Ivan Dědek:** Writing – review & editing. **Vojtěch Kupka:** Writing – review & editing. **Jan Urbánek:** Investigation. **David Panáček:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Michal Otyepka:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

MO has share in InSiliBio, Ltd. and ATOMIVER, Ltd. companies. Other authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the ERDF/ESF project TECHSCALE (No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004587) and ERDF/ESF project 'Interdisciplinary Approaches to the Prevention and Diagnosis of Viral Diseases' (CZ.02.01.01/00/23_021/0008856). Additional funding was provided by the Research Infrastructure NanoEnviCz, supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic under Project No LM2023066. D.P. & M.O. acknowledge the financial support of the European Union under the REFRESH – Research Excellence for Region Sustainability and High-tech Industries project number CZ.10.03.01/00/22_003/0000048 via the Operational Programme Just Transition. The authors gratefully thank Anežka Šindlerová and Renata Jakubcová (electrochemical experiments), Jiří Hošek (SEM), Eirini Ioannou (SEM), Jana Stráská (TEM), Klára Čépe (AFM), Oleksandr Riabonenko and Gifty Jacob (STA-EGA).

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.electacta.2026.148780](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2026.148780).

Data availability

Data are available via ZENODO repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19330900>.

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